

Microsoft Activation Scripts (MAS): A Basic Introduction to Command Prompt-Based Windows Tools

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Abstract

Microsoft Activation Script (MAS) is an open source software tools created by massgrave, designed for checking and troubleshooting the Windows and Office products using various activation methods such as Ohook and online injection. This Command Prompt script can run on both 32 bit and 64 bit Windows operating systems to execute the system troubleshooting quickly, but this activity is unofficial. In addition, this program is also allows users to check the Windows information system installed on the computer even without an internet connection. Another advantage of this program is its simple and user-friendly interface, so both beginners and more experienced users can use it effectively. With this tool, users not only benefit from an verification process but also have quick access to important information about this operating system.


```
Administrator: Troubleshoot 2.7

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[1] Help
-----
[2] Dism RestoreHealth
[3] SFC Scannow

[4] Fix WHI
[5] Fix Licensing
[6] Fix WPA Registry

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[0] Go back
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Choose a menu option using your keyboard :
_
```

INTRODUCTION

Microsoft Activation Scripts (MAS) is a open source Command Prompt scripts created by an anonym open source software developer named massgrave, who actively shares software development instructions on computer forums on the internet, and this program or scripts can be run on computer or laptop with Windows operating systems "x86 and x64" architecture for troubleshooting Windows and Office services easily and quickly, so this tool or program can also be used to easily check the Windows information system installed on the computer online or without connected to internet connection.

CONTENTS

With so many ways or methods available, Windows troubleshooting and verification should definitely not be done indiscriminately. A danger operations will likely lead to device insecurity and loss of privacy protection measures. Therefore, you can try or test using the Microsoft Activation Scripts to perform the analyze and system checking. This Windows checking process is very important for users, because to ensure that system in Windows is running optimal.

Microsoft Activation Scripts (MAS) have become a tool for many Windows and Office users, providing a solution for system troubleshooting, checking and monitoring, as long as they are used carefully and responsibly. But, this program is unofficial. The file size of this program is a few KB, this is easy to implement and familiar to almost all people or the general public without a technical background.

Here's how Microsoft Activation Scripts works: It searches for and inserts (hook and inject) an unused system license from an available server and automatically applies it to a Windows computer system.

And here's how to download the Massgrave's Microsoft Activation Scripts setup file and how to use it on Windows:


```
Administrator: Microsoft Activation Scripts 2.7

Activation Methods:

[1] HWID | Windows | Permanent
[2] Ohook | Office | Permanent
[3] KMS38 | Windows | Year 2038
[4] Online KMS | Windows / Office | 180 Days

[5] Check Activation Status
[6] Change Windows Edition
[7] Change Office Edition

[8] Troubleshoot
[9] Extras
[H] Help
[0] Exit

Choose a menu option using your keyboard [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,H,0] :
```

1. Download the Microsoft Activation Scripts cmd file from <https://massgrave.dev>
2. Once the file is downloaded, open the cmd file by double-click or right-clicking and selecting "Run as administrator"
3. Once the program is finished being opened, a simple screen will appear with all menu and can be selected following the on screen instructions.
4. In the screen that appears, the user can use it according to the required needs.

CONCLUSION

This is a brief explanation of massgrave's Microsoft Activation Scripts an installation and system checker scripts for Windows operating system. Of course, with so many computer programs available today, from the perspective of users and developers, they will look different, especially for users who need to be able to pay attention to a changes in the information that currently exists. And, must to know this activity is not trully safe.

References:

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